

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

D3.3 Bio-based solutions innovation report

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Executive Summary

This Bio-based Solutions Innovation Report presents the outcomes of the BioRural project's national multi-actor workshops, which were designed to engage diverse stakeholders in rural communities across Europe. A total of 43 workshops were conducted across 14 countries covering three overlapping themes (i) inland raw material production, (ii) aquatic raw material production, and (iii) biological raw material processing.

To effectively capture the grassroots-level opinions of stakeholders across 14 countries, an innovative workshop series was developed. This series was specifically designed to engage key bioeconomy stakeholders and gather insights on the transition to circular bio-based value chains.

The main innovations emerging from the workshops were centered around 'waste' management and the reuse of residues and byproducts from existing value chains. This focus reflects the importance of maximizing resource efficiency by repurposing byproducts and waste to create new bio-based products. Innovations in this area aimed to reduce waste while creating valuable products, such as bioenergy and bioplastics, from byproducts of agricultural, forestry, and industrial activities. Another prominent theme was the development of sustainable materials, with many ideas focused on replacing conventional fossil-based materials with bio-based alternatives. The main bio-based product ideas revolved around agricultural products, such as bio-based fertilizers, bioplastics made from agricultural residues, and bioenergy from crop residues, which were seen as essential for reducing the environmental impact of current production systems.

The main challenges identified during the workshops included high costs associated with transitioning to and implementing circular value chains, significant research and technological gaps, and regulatory barriers that impede the development and scaling of bio-based innovations. High costs were particularly tied to the logistics of feedstock collection, the development of processing technologies, and the lack of infrastructure necessary to support circular systems. Research gaps were also highlighted, particularly in areas such as biorefining technologies and residues valorization processes, where current technologies are not yet efficient or scalable enough to meet industry needs. Additionally, regulatory challenges—such as unclear waste classifications, byproducts definitions and inconsistent policies across regions—further complicated the adoption of circular bio-based practices.

To overcome these barriers, several key solutions were proposed. First, there is a need to simplify and clarify regulations, particularly around waste management and the classification of bio-based products, to encourage the reuse of byproducts and streamline circular practices. Stakeholders also suggested continued support for research and innovation, especially in closing technological gaps related to processing efficiencies, advanced biorefineries, and recycling technologies. Investment in these areas will be critical to reducing the costs of bio-based products and making circular systems more competitive with conventional alternatives. In addition, fostering regional bioeconomy clusters, where local industries can collaborate to share resources and infrastructure, was seen as an effective strategy for addressing logistical challenges and promoting the growth of circular value chains.

Overall, the insights gained from these workshops provide a foundation for shaping future policy recommendations coming out of the BioRural Project and accelerate the transition to a more circular bioeconomy.

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1 Introduction

This Bio-based Solutions Innovation Report presents the outcomes of the BioRural project's national multi-actor workshops, which were designed to engage diverse stakeholders in rural communities across Europe. A total of 43 workshops were conducted, with each of the 14 participating countries hosting 3 to 4 workshops. The workshops were organized around three key focus areas: (i) inland raw material production, (ii) aquatic raw material production, and (iii) biological raw material processing. These sessions were interactive and collaborative, aiming to gather feedback from local stakeholders on how bio-based solutions can be adapted to meet rural needs. The objectives were threefold: to explore ways for bio-based solutions to reach rural communities and be implemented locally, to generate innovative new uses for existing bio-based solutions, and to capture grassroots-level ideas and innovations from stakeholders in rural areas. Collectively, the workshops covered over 140 value chains offering a rich source of insights for future bio-based value chain development.

In the context of the European Green Deal [1], the EU Bioeconomy Strategy[2], and the Circular Economy Action Plan [3], significant transformations across economic sectors are required. A critical part of this transformation is the development of a circular bioeconomy, which can provide essential feedstocks to the wider circular economy and produce bio-based products that replace fossil-based alternatives. However, this transition faces key challenges including the reliance on linear value chains, traditional production models, rural demographic challenges, and policy gaps. The current economic model in many value chains, including bio-based ones, is based on linear value chains, where resources are extracted, used, and then discarded as waste. This "take-make-dispose" approach is in stark contrast to the principles of a circular bioeconomy, which emphasizes resource efficiency, waste minimization, and the continual reuse and recycling of materials. The transition to circular value chains requires a fundamental shift in how resources are managed, from the design of products to end-of-life solutions [4]. For bio-based industries, this involves developing sustainable supply chains that can ensure the continuous use of biological resources without depleting ecosystems. Overcoming this challenge necessitates significant innovation in both technological solutions and business models, as well as strong coordination across sectors and value chain actors.

In addition, many industries, particularly those in rural areas, still rely heavily on traditional, resource-intensive production models that are optimized for efficiency and cost rather than sustainability [5]. These models often prioritize short-term economic gains over long-term environmental stewardship, making it difficult to integrate bio-based solutions that may require initial investments in new technologies, practices, or infrastructure. For instance, transitioning to bio-based alternatives may require retooling existing manufacturing processes, investing in new technologies for biomass processing, or adopting new farming practices for feedstock production. Rural areas, which are crucial for the production of bio-based raw materials, also face unique demographic challenges that complicate the transition to a circular bioeconomy. Many rural regions in Europe are experiencing population decline, aging populations, and a lack of skilled labor, all of which limit their capacity to adopt and implement new bio-based solutions.

While the EU has laid out ambitious strategies like the Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan, the implementation of these policies at the local and national levels often lags behind. In some cases, there are conflicting regulations that make it difficult for bio-based industries to scale. For example, policies related to waste management, agricultural practices, or industrial production may not be aligned to support circular bio-based solutions.

Capturing the perspectives of grassroots stakeholders, especially bioeconomy practitioners such as primary feedstock producers and bio-based industries, is vital for this transformation. These stakeholders offer valuable, evidence-based insights into the transition to circular bio-based value chains. Their input not only provides innovative ideas for bio-based solutions but also highlights specific challenges and opportunities from a policy standpoint.

This report also outlines the methodology employed to capture and analyze the feedback gathered from the workshops. It presents the key results and findings, including an in-depth analysis of the ideas and innovations identified. This is followed by a discussion of the implications of these findings in relation to the broader European policy landscape. The results of this report will feed into the later stages of the BioRural project, particularly in the formulation of policy recommendations aimed at facilitating the transition to a circular bioeconomy.

2. Methodology

The methodology used for these workshops follows a structured approach designed to capture, analyze, and synthesize insights from grassroots stakeholders across rural regions in Europe. To effectively capture the grassroots-level opinions of stakeholders across 14 countries, an innovative workshop series was developed. This series was specifically designed to engage key bioeconomy stakeholders and gather insights on the transition to circular bio-based value chains. The workshops employed a structured, interactive format that facilitated knowledge exchange and fostered collaborative thinking. Each workshop began with knowledge-sharing sessions, where biobased solutions, survey results and BioRural success stories were presented. These sessions provided a common understanding of the existing linear value chains and the potential of circular models. Following these discussions, a series of interactive exercises were conducted to further deepen stakeholder engagement. These exercises tasked participants with reimagining and redesigning existing value chains, focusing on how to make them more sustainable and circular.

Participants were encouraged to identify key innovations within their specific value chains, exploring new technologies, practices, and business models that could accelerate the transition to a circular bioeconomy. Additionally, they worked collectively to pinpoint the critical challenges that hinder this transformation, such as technological limitations, regulatory barriers, or market constraints. Finally, the workshops facilitated brainstorming sessions to develop practical solutions to overcome these challenges, with an emphasis on collaboration across sectors and the need for supportive policy frameworks. This multi-step process allowed stakeholders to share their experiences and knowledge as well as to co-create innovative strategies for transforming bio-based value chains in line with the goals of a circular economy.

Each workshop was implemented by local partner(s) of the BioRural project in their local language. The following section outlines the guidance given to all partners in designing the workshops. Partners were required to follow the structure in terms of thematic focus, include knowledge exchange activities, and the interactive exercises. Some flexibility was provided to partners to implement the workshops according to local conditions.

2.1 Structure of the workshops

To comprehensively address the key themes of the bioeconomy—such as food and agriculture, forestry and natural habitats, aquatic and water systems, bioenergy, and biomaterials—the workshops were structured around three broad thematic areas: (i) inland biological feedstock, (ii) aquatic biological feedstock, and (iii) bio-based industries and services (see Figure 1). In each country, the plan was to hold one workshop per theme, ensuring coverage of the primary and secondary production systems, as well as processing industries related to bio-based sectors.

Figure 1. Thematic Division of Workshops

The workshops were specifically designed with the following objectives in mind:

- Disseminate relevant results from the BioRural project to key stakeholders.

- Strengthen the BioRural network, the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN), and the BioRural Toolkit.
- Gather and provide feedback on how bio-based solutions can be effectively introduced into rural communities and adopted in local practice.
- Facilitate the generation of innovative uses for existing bio-based solutions.
- Capture grassroots-level ideas and innovations from rural stakeholders, aiming to identify at least 60 ideas or needs (with 15 per Rural Bioeconomy Partnership).

Each workshop was planned as a half-day event, structured into key segments that included introductions, brief presentations on the BioRural project, and three interactive exercises designed to produce actionable outputs. The workshops were intended to take place in-person, with virtual formats considered only in exceptional cases. To ensure that the workshops were both practical and relevant to the participants, the venues were selected based on the following criteria:

- Located in or near rural areas, to better engage with the local context.
- Capable of comfortably hosting 20-30 participants, as the interactive format required team-based activities.
- Easily accessible to participants, with proximity to a relevant case study or bioeconomy facility that could serve as an optional site visit.

The option to incorporate a visit to nearby facilities, such as bio-based processing plants or innovative agricultural setups, was at the discretion of the workshop organizer, depending on time and participant interest.

Each workshop was intended to include a range of relevant stakeholders to the theme of the workshop with a specific emphasis on bioeconomy practitioners. Each workshop was intended to have 20-30 participants per workshop (these numbers are flexible based on your local conditions). The proposed non-exhaustive list of stakeholders included:

- Producers/processors of bio-based raw materials
- Researchers and academics in the field of the bioeconomy
- Technology/industry providers
- Advisors
- Policymakers and state officials
- Local/Regional waste management companies
- Municipal authorities
- Civil society actors
- Energy Cooperatives
- Other actors who are active in the sector of bio-economy

Each workshop was intended as a half-day event. A proposed agenda blueprint is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Proposed workshop agenda blueprint

Time	Topic	Comment
09:00 – 09:20	Introductions and ice breaker	The ice breaker will not be on the official agenda but it’s a good idea to get people involved and interested. We propose that each participant briefly

		introduces themselves in 30 seconds and answers the icebreaker. For suggestions for the ice breaker see below.
09:20 – 09:30	The BioRural project and methodology and goals of workshop	A short introduction/presentation of BioRural followed by an explanation of how the workshop will run
09:30 – 09:45	Survey results	Give a brief overview of the results of the surveys with a particular focus on the results of your country
09:45 – 10:00	Success story / case study presentation	Present relevant success stories of the project and the most relevant bio-based solutions in the inventory
10:00 – 10:30	Exercise 1	See section below
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break	
11:00 – 11:15	Exercise 2	See section below
11:15 – 11:30	Exercise 3	See section below
11:30 – 12:30	Presentations and Discussion	10-minute presentation per group followed by a short discussion for each group. Then a general discussion
12:30 – 13:00	Evaluation and Closing remarks	Vote on the designs takes place. Then the organizers recap the workshop and invite participants to the Regional Workshop.
13:00+	Light lunch	Informally present voting outcome.

2.2 Capturing biobased innovations

To effectively capture bio-based innovations and grassroots opinions on the transition to circular value chains, an interactive and collaborative workshop concept was designed, consisting of three key exercises. Participants were divided into small groups of 4-6 people (depending on the total number of participants), with around five members per group. The composition of each group was carefully curated to ensure diversity, with an optimal mix including

at least one researcher, one technology or industry provider, one advisor, one producer or processor, and one policymaker.

Circular Economy

The three main principles of the circular economy, which are driven by design, are: (a) minimise inputs and eliminate waste and pollution, (b) circulate products and materials (i.e. extend their lifecycle), and (c) regenerate nature.

re-design the value chain of [feedstock/industry/product] by applying the principles of the circular economy all along the chain = close the circle by imagining how the linear system could be transformed into a sustainable and circular value chain.

Note the specific technologies and practices (bio-based solutions) included in your design.

Remember to check the page behind to guide you through the exercise.

INLAND BIOLOGICAL FEEDSTOCK / AQUATIC BIOLOGICAL FEEDSTOCK / BIOBASED INDUSTRY - SERVICE

Capture Innovative Ideas

Describe with some detail the 3 most innovative ideas coming out of your circular solution

INNOVATIVE IDEA

- 1
- 2
- 3

Challenges & Ways to overcome them

Identify the 3 main challenges in making your design a reality

Propose ways to overcome these challenges

Figure 2. Screenshot of part of the canvas used to redesign circular value chains

The workshop aimed to be both participatory and interactive, ensuring that the outputs would be actionable and directly relevant to the bioeconomy. To achieve this, all exercises were designed to align with the key objectives of the workshops: to gather and provide feedback on how bio-based solutions can be integrated into rural communities and implemented in local practices; to foster the generation of innovative uses for existing bio-based solutions; to capture grassroots-level ideas and innovations from rural stakeholders, with the goal of identifying at least 60 ideas or needs (15 per RBP).

2.2.1 Exercise 1: Close the circle

Participants were tasked with designing a circular system with the starting point being an inland biological feedstock, aquatic biological feedstock or bio-based industry or product, depending on the theme of the workshop. Each group had to choose their own feedstock/biobased-industry/product and be relevant to the local area/country (4-5 suggestions of potential feedstock/biobased-industry/product were provided). Based on this, each group is tasked with designing the entire circular value chain for this feedstock/biobased industry/product. The driving goal here was: to design the value chain of [feedstock/industry/product] by applying the principles of the circular economy all along the chain. In other words, to close the circle by imagining how existing value chains could be transformed into sustainable and circular value chains.

Instructions for the exercise included:

- Participants were provided with a pre-designed canvas that depicted a traditional, linear value chain, which they were instructed to conceptually redesign into a circular system. They were also given space to note key challenges and potential solutions to making this transformation.
- A brief introduction to the circular economy, including a comparison with the linear model, was given by the organizing committee to help set the stage for the activity.
- Participants were first asked to design the traditional linear value chain currently in use for their selected feedstock or product. A checklist of common problems with linear models was provided to stimulate critical thinking.
- Following this, the participants were tasked with reimagining the value chain as a circular system, identifying inputs and outputs at each stage of the process and considering technologies and processes needed to close the loop.

2.2.2 Exercise 2: Make it tighter

In the second exercise, participants were encouraged to refine and improve their circular value chain designs by making them even more circular, innovative, and sustainable. To assist with this, a board was presented that showcased existing bio-based solutions, including technologies and practices. The goal was for participants to integrate these solutions into their designs, making adjustments where necessary to optimize circularity.

The driving question for this exercise was:

- "Considering these solutions (technologies and practices), would you change anything in your value chain to make it more circular?"

At the end of the exercise, each group was asked to identify and describe in detail two key innovations within their circular design, explaining which aspects of their proposed solution were the most innovative.

2.2.3 Exercise 3: What's stopping us?

The third exercise focused on identifying the challenges that could hinder the implementation of the group's circular value chain in real-world rural contexts. Participants were asked to think critically about the practicalities of bringing their designs to life and to discuss potential barriers.

The driving question for this exercise was:

- "What do you expect to be the three main challenges (and their solutions) in making your value chain circular?"

This exercise was intended to highlight the real-world constraints and obstacles that rural stakeholders might face in transitioning to circular bio-based systems, such as regulatory, financial, technological, or logistical challenges.

2.2.4 Post-exercise presentation and evaluation

At the end of the three exercises, each group presented their design to the rest of the participants and respond to any questions, comments or suggestions that might come up ('presentations and discussions'). At the end of the presentations each participant was given an evaluation sheet asking them to evaluate each group's proposed circular value chain.

2.2.5 Post-workshop Requirements

Upon completion of each workshop, partners were required to submit detailed reports summarizing the activities and outcomes. These reports included translated data from the workshop exercises, the completed canvases, and a short analysis of the findings. The reports were submitted to the Task Leader, CERTH, where they were compiled and analyzed to contribute to this deliverable.

This post-workshop reporting process ensured that the insights and innovations generated during the workshops were systematically captured, evaluated, and incorporated into the broader goals of the BioRural project.

2.3 Task Timeline

Below is the initial proposed timeline for the workshops, which was agreed upon by all project partners. However, in practice, minor delays were experienced in the holding of some workshops due to country-specific challenges, such as logistical issues, stakeholder availability, and local circumstances. Despite these delays, all partners successfully completed their workshops and submitted their detailed reports by August 2024.

Month	6			12			18			24		
Develop Material and Strategy for workshops (CERTH)												
Prepare venue and workshops (all partners)												
Carry out workshops (all partners)												
Write and prepare workshop reports (all partners)												
Prepare deliverable (CERTH)											D3.3	
Integrate material in toolkit (all partners)												

Figure 3. Proposed timeline of the task

Table 2. Dates when workshops were held

Country	Inland biological feedstock	Aquatic biological feedstock	Biobased industries and services
Greece (CERTH, FSH, ICO)	16.11.2023	02.04.2024	13-14.12.2023
North Macedonia (GGP)	18.12.2023	09.04.2024	13.03.2024
Romania (GEA)	25.10.2023	20.03.2024	16.11.2023
Slovenia (UL, ALGEN)	8.03.2024	07.11.2023	23.5.2024
Italy (AIEL)	08.09.2023 +27.03.2024		08.05.2024
Portugal (UC, CBE)	22.11.2023	04.06.2024	22.03.2024
Spain (AVEBIOM)	17.10.2023 + 24.10.2023	30.04.2024	02.11.2023
Latvia (LLU)	21.03.2024	22.03.2024	20.03.2024
Lithuania (VDU)	30.11.2023	15.11.2023	07.12.2023
Poland (IUNG)	05.03.2024	29.02.2024	13.03.2024
Denmark (AU)	25.09.2023	28.05.2024	15.05.2024

The Netherlands (DELPHY)	28.01.2024	27.06.2024	15.05.2024
Germany (IZES)	16.11.2023	23.04.2024	27.08.2024
France (Valorial, Natureplast)	09.11.2023	31.05.2024	12.10.2023

2.4 Methodology of analysis

The analysis of the workshop reports followed a systematic approach aimed at extracting key insights on bio-based innovations, challenges, and opportunities across diverse value chains. The methodology combined both qualitative and quantitative elements, although the emphasis was placed on qualitative interpretation to capture the nuances of the value chains covered. Below is an outline of the key steps and considerations in the analysis process.

The primary method for analyzing the workshop results involved a qualitative review of the data. This review was used to identify innovative product ideas, key challenges, and overarching themes across various bio-based value chains. Facilitators’ notes, participant contributions, and group outputs from the workshops were thoroughly examined to find insights into how bio-based solutions are currently being adopted and how they can be further developed to promote a circular bioeconomy. Particular attention was given to capturing grassroots-level perspectives, which offered unique and practical viewpoints on the transition to circular value chains.

To organize the diverse data from the workshops, the outputs were categorized into major sectors relevant to the bioeconomy. These sectors included agriculture, bioenergy, biomaterials, water systems, and forestry. By sorting the data into these categories, the analysis allowed for easier comparison across different sectors and value chains. This categorization also enabled a more focused examination of sector-specific innovations and challenges, providing insights tailored to each bio-based industry.

From the qualitative data, specific bio-based product ideas were identified, with an emphasis on their innovative potential and alignment with sustainability goals. The analysis aimed to highlight products that demonstrated novel approaches or applications, particularly those that could support the circular economy. Relevant product examples were extracted based on their potential to replace fossil-based products or introduce new processes that reduce environmental impact.

While the analysis was largely qualitative, some quantitative insights were provided. Counts were made of the frequency of certain ideas, challenges, or themes that emerged across the workshops. However, these counts were primarily used to support the qualitative findings and provide a sense of scale or prevalence, rather than being the primary focus of the analysis. To further refine the data, a keyword filtering process was used. Specific keywords such as "bioenergy," "packaging," "biomaterials," and other bio-based industry-related terms were applied to filter product-related ideas, innovations, and challenges. This approach helped streamline the analysis by grouping ideas and identifying patterns within particular value chains, allowing for a more targeted review of the workshop outputs.

As part of the analysis, the most innovative ideas and value chains were prioritized based on several criteria. The top 10 most promising products or ideas were selected according to their novelty, scalability, and relevance to the broader bioeconomy. These ideas were then ranked in two categories:

1. **Impact and Feasibility:** How significant the potential impact of the idea is on the bioeconomy, and how feasible it is to implement within current or near-term market conditions.
2. **Scalability, Value, and Resource Requirements:** How scalable the innovation is across regions and industries, its overall economic and societal value, the resources required for its development, and the funding needed for a lean start-up or collaborative project.

Expert stakeholders conducted these rankings, and ideas that scored a 6 or above on both measures were deemed practical and worthy of further exploration. For instances where value chain descriptions were too general, an “NA” (Not Applicable) remark was given to indicate the lack of sufficient detail for proper assessment.

2.5 Limitations

The analysis of the workshop reports faced several limitations. One of the primary challenges was generic reporting, where some data entries lacked the detailed context needed for thorough analysis. In certain cases, the information provided by the workshops was too vague or generalized, making it difficult to categorize innovations or fully assess their potential impact. While the overall framework for the workshops was consistent, variations in the way they were executed in different countries meant that not all workshops generated the same type or depth of data. This inconsistency made it challenging to compare the results from different regions, as some workshops provided detailed, actionable insights while others yielded more generalized information.

Another significant challenge was the synthesis of broad qualitative data. Given that much of the data was qualitative in nature, transforming these diverse inputs into coherent themes and actionable insights required subjective interpretation. This reliance on subjective judgment in synthesizing the results may have introduced biases in the analysis, particularly in terms of prioritizing certain ideas or innovations over others. Efforts were made to mitigate these biases by using a diversity of expert and facilitator interpretations. Since the analysis involved evaluating innovative ideas based on subjective criteria such as novelty, scalability, and feasibility, there was potential for bias in how certain innovations were perceived and ranked. This subjectivity may have led to the overemphasis of some ideas while underrepresenting others.

Overall, these limitations underline the inherent complexity of analyzing grassroots-level innovations in a project involving diverse stakeholders and regions. While these challenges constrained some aspects of the analysis, the methodology was designed to extract as much meaningful insight as possible, and the findings still provide valuable guidance for the ongoing development of bio-based value chains in the circular bioeconomy.

3. Results

This section provides the results coming out of the 43 national workshops. For access to all results and data please follow the links provided in the Annex.

3.1 Generic Results

In total, 43 workshops were held across 14 countries, with the participation of 1,078 stakeholders (see Figure 3.), representing various sectors of the bioeconomy. These workshops covered 140 value chains, each exploring specific challenges and opportunities for transitioning toward circular bioeconomy models. Value chains ranged from agriculture, such as crop and livestock production, to forestry and aquaculture, including fish farming and marine resources. Other sectors included food processing, bioplastics, and bioenergy, highlighting the diversity of industries involved in the circular bioeconomy transition.

Figure 4. Number of participants and value chains covered by country

In terms of themes, a total of 13 workshops focused on aquatic feedstocks and their value chains, 14 on bio-based industries and services, and 16 on inland biological feedstocks and their value chains were held (see Figure 4). Inherently, when analyzing entire value chains, some overlap occurs between these themes. For example, while workshops on inland biological feedstock value chains often also touched on aspects of processing and bio-based industries, the primary focus remained on the designated theme of the workshop. This overlap highlights the interconnected nature of bio-based systems, where multiple stages of the value chain, from raw material production to final product development, are closely intertwined. However, despite these intersections, each workshop maintained a thematic focus to ensure that specific aspects of the bioeconomy were thoroughly explored.

Figure 5. Number of workshops held by theme

Stakeholders represented a diverse mix of sectors, including feedstock producers, industry representatives, research institutions, local communities, and governmental bodies. The predominant type of stakeholder were bioeconomy business related stakeholders/practitioners such as farmers, foresters, aquaculture operators, and industry professionals, brought practical insights and real-world experience to the discussions on transforming value chains into circular bioeconomy models

3.2 Innovations

The workshops generated many innovative ideas aimed at driving the transition to a circular bioeconomy. For full access to all results and data please follow the links provided in the Annex. The analysis of value chain ideas generated during the workshops revealed a wide range of innovations, from simple optimization techniques to the implementation of advanced biotechnology solutions. The ideas were generally context-specific, reflecting the diverse bio-based systems across different countries and regions. For instance, some value chains focused on optimizing current processes by improving resource efficiency or integrating new technologies, while others introduced entirely new biotechnological processes aimed at creating more circular and sustainable bioeconomy systems.

3.2.1 Innovative ‘keyword’ mentions across value chains

In terms of keyword focus (only counted once per workshop), waste management (mainly related to the reuse of residues and by-products from existing processes) was the most frequently discussed area, mentioned 46 times. Stakeholders particularly emphasized innovations focused on reducing waste and managing residues, such as producing biochar from agricultural residues. Sustainable materials also played a key role, with 30 mentions of alternative materials like biodegradable plastics. Innovations in water management were reported 28 times, particularly technologies for optimizing water use in agriculture. Additionally, fertilizer alternatives (26 mentions) were proposed as replacements for chemical fertilizers, leveraging organic waste streams. Improving energy efficiency (23 mentions) through energy-efficient biorefining and biomass use (18 mentions) for bioenergy were also critical themes. Other notable areas of innovation included carbon reduction (9 mentions), resource optimization (6 mentions), and recycling innovations (5 mentions), alongside emerging solutions in bioplastics development, sustainability, resource efficiency, and renewable resources.

Figure 6. Number of innovations reported by theme

A significant focus across the workshops was on residues management, with numerous ideas centered around reusing or repurposing residues from existing value chains for other processes or products. This emphasis on residues demonstrates stakeholder recognition of the importance of closing loops within value chains, turning what would traditionally be considered waste into valuable inputs for new products. These innovations are particularly relevant for industries looking to reduce their environmental impact while improving overall efficiency. In several cases, value chains explored using agricultural or biomass residues as feedstock for bioenergy production, bioplastics, or other biomaterials, thus creating new revenue streams and reducing the need for virgin resources.

This has various implications for bioeconomy feedstocks. Many of the innovations discussed during the workshops focused on increasing the efficiency of bio-based feedstocks, ensuring that more can be extracted or utilized from the same amount of raw material. This drive towards efficiency also ties into the development of advanced biorefineries, which can process multiple types of biomass and convert them into a variety of products such as biofuels, chemicals, and biomaterials. These biorefineries represent a critical step in the evolution of the bioeconomy, enabling more sustainable and diversified uses of bio-based resources. Moreover, the integration of biotechnology in value chains shows promise in enhancing the sustainability of feedstock production, improving both the environmental and economic viability of bio-based industries. By optimizing biological processes and creating new materials from bio-based inputs, advanced biotechnological solutions are helping to reshape traditional value chains into more circular systems.

3.2.2 Ideas for biobased products

The analysis of bio-based product ideas and innovations, as shown in Figure 6, highlights a strong emphasis on agricultural products, which emerged as the most commonly discussed category, followed by food products, recycling and waste-derived products, and packaging and materials. The focus on agricultural products reflects the central role that bio-based solutions play in optimizing agricultural systems and utilizing bio-residues, particularly within rural economies. The diverse range of ideas generated showcases the potential for creating innovative, sustainable products from locally available resources.

Figure 7. Specific Biobased products ideas/innovations captured by theme

A prominent example is the recycling of agricultural residues and byproducts into new products. This includes innovative ideas such as reusing pumice stone from exhausted agricultural substrates to create products like cosmetics. Similarly, sustainable fertilizer solutions, such as biochar and composting, were widely discussed as key approaches to improving soil health and reducing reliance on synthetic fertilizers.

In water systems there was a focus on locally sourced fish feed, which can be derived from various streams of bio-residues, offering a sustainable alternative to conventional fish feed in the aquaculture industry. This aligns with the growing need for more localized, circular food production systems that reduce dependency on imported feedstocks and make better use of available bio-residues.

A key topic centered on bio-based construction materials, stakeholders proposed innovative materials such as straw, buckwheat, hemp, wood, and composite boards. These materials offer environmentally friendly alternatives to conventional construction resources, supporting the development of sustainable buildings. Another key topic was the development of biodegradable packaging solutions, which include materials derived from algae, shellfish, insect waste, and mussels, as well as bioplastics. These solutions respond to the growing demand for alternatives to fossil-based plastics, contributing to the reduction of plastic waste and enhancing the circular economy within the packaging sector.

Several value chain ideas centered on the use of integrated bioenergy systems, particularly in the form of pellets and biogas. These ideas aim to make better use of agricultural residues and bio-residues to produce renewable energy, supporting the transition to a more sustainable energy system. The integration of local consortia to manage bio-residues was also proposed, offering a collaborative approach to efficiently handling bio-residues at a community level.

3.2.3 Innovations per bioeconomy theme

3.2.3.1 Food and agriculture

Several innovative ideas emerged from the inland biological feedstock workshops, with a common focus on using agricultural byproducts to create bio-based fertilizers. These suggestions, explored in countries like Germany, Poland, and France, aim to develop locally sourced fertilizers from wood and agricultural residues, offering a sustainable alternative to chemical fertilizers. Despite its potential, this solution faces regulatory challenges related to the approval and distribution of bio-based fertilizers. Additionally, logistical issues, such as the efficient collection and processing of raw materials from forestry and agricultural operations, must be addressed to enable large-scale implementation.

Another prominent innovation is the valorization of biomass from agricultural prunings, a concept explored across multiple countries. This initiative involves processing agricultural prunings into bioenergy or biomaterials, promoting circularity in agriculture by turning residues into valuable products. Local consortia are being supported economically to facilitate this process. However, the logistics of collecting and transporting biomass from rural areas, where infrastructure is often underdeveloped, remains a key challenge to scaling this innovation.

In Spain, Portugal, and Italy, the establishment of hubs for organic residues processing was a notable idea. These hubs aim to collect and process organic residues from farms, converting it into bio-based products such as compost and fertilizers, thus reducing agricultural waste and promoting a closed-loop system. However, setting up these hubs involves high costs, and the logistics of processing large volumes of residues efficiently presents significant operational challenges. Additionally, community composting of organic waste was an innovation highlighted in Romania, where rural and peri-urban households are encouraged to compost their organic waste. This initiative helps divert organic waste from landfills, creating valuable soil improvers for local agriculture. While it offers clear environmental and agricultural benefits, adoption rates remain low in some regions due to limited awareness and education around composting practices, which hinders its scalability.

Table 3. Key examples of Innovative ideas in food and agriculture systems

Innovative Idea	Country	Short Description
Bio-based fertilizers from wood and agricultural byproducts	Germany, Poland, France	Creating locally sourced bio-based fertilizers from wood and agricultural residues as a sustainable alternative to chemical fertilizers.
Biomass valorization from agricultural prunings	All	Processing agricultural prunings into bioenergy or biomaterials to promote circularity and reduce agricultural waste.
Hubs for organic residues processing	Spain, Portugal, Italy	Establishing hubs to collect and process organic residues from farms, turning residues into bio-based products such as compost and fertilizers.
Community composting of organic waste	Romania	Encouraging rural and peri-urban households to compost organic waste, creating soil improvers while reducing landfill waste.

3.2.3.2 Forestry and natural habitats

Several innovative ideas emerged from the workshops focused on forestry, particularly on how to better utilize wood and forestry byproducts. Like the agricultural sector there was a focus on the development of bio-based fertilizers from wood and forestry residues. This approach offers a sustainable alternative to conventional chemical fertilizers by using locally sourced organic materials.

In Italy and Spain, a notable innovation is the valorization of biomass from forestry prunings, which involves processing pruned materials into bioenergy and biomaterials. This concept promotes circularity within the forestry industry by turning residues into valuable products, reducing the environmental impact of forestry operations. However, the primary obstacle is logistical, as the collection and transportation of biomass from rural or remote forested areas can be difficult to manage without improved infrastructure.

Another emerging trend is the use of wood residues for biochar production, a concept that has been explored in Poland, Latvia, and Italy. Forestry residues, which are often left behind after logging, are processed into biochar, a valuable product that improves soil quality and sequesters carbon. This innovation empowers local actors to optimize material collection and processing, contributing to both environmental sustainability and agricultural productivity. However, challenges remain in ensuring a consistent supply of high-quality residues and establishing the infrastructure needed for efficient biochar production.

In Italy, ash from biomass burning in power plants is being repurposed as a soil improver. This innovation leverages the byproducts of bioenergy production. The establishment of collection centers for ash is proposed to streamline the process, but funding remains a significant barrier. Without the financial resources to build and operate these collection and processing facilities, scaling this solution will be difficult.

In the wood furniture manufacturing sector, Denmark is exploring the use of non-toxic, sustainable wood finishes. This innovation responds to growing consumer demand for eco-friendly products by replacing traditional chemical-based finishes with natural alternatives. While this solution enhances the sustainability of wood products and aligns with market trends, it faces challenges in terms of cost. Natural finishes are often more expensive than conventional options, making it difficult for manufacturers to scale the use of these eco-friendly alternatives without significant cost reduction or market incentives.

Table 4. Key examples of Innovative ideas in forestry systems

Innovative Idea	Country	Short Description
Bio-based fertilizers from wood residues	Germany, France	Creating bio-based fertilizers from wood and forestry residues to replace chemical fertilizers.
Valorization of biomass from forestry prunings	Italy, Spain	Processing forestry prunings into bioenergy and biomaterials, promoting circularity.
Wood residues used for biochar production	Poland, Latvia, Italy	Converting wood residues from forestry operations into biochar for soil improvement.
Ash from biomass for soil improvers	Italy	Converting ash from biomass burning in power plants into soil improvers and other products.
Non-toxic wood finishes for furniture	Denmark	Using sustainable, non-toxic wood finishes in furniture production to meet eco-friendly market demands.

3.2.3.3 Aquatic and water systems

Several innovative ideas emerged from the aquaculture sector, each focused on improving sustainability and resource efficiency. One key innovation involves the development of Seawater Cubes, a system designed to create controlled, sustainable fish farming environments. This approach, explored in Germany, allows fish farms to operate more efficiently while minimizing their environmental impact by closely regulating water quality and other key parameters. However, a significant challenge remains in securing the necessary funding to launch and scale these projects, as the initial investment required is substantial.

In Portugal and Greece, another innovative concept centers on the repurposing of rejected fish from aquaculture by drying and milling them into fish flour or fish oil. This solution aims to reduce waste in aquaculture by converting fish that are unsuitable for sale into valuable resources. The major obstacle for this innovation is the current lack

of infrastructure needed to properly collect and process rejected fish. Establishing an efficient system for handling this waste stream is essential for scaling the solution effectively.

The idea of circular aquaculture is also gaining traction, with software tools being used to identify and repurpose various residues within aquaculture systems. By improving resource efficiency and reusing materials that would otherwise be discarded, circular aquaculture can significantly reduce waste and lower the environmental footprint of fish farming operations. However, meeting strict environmental regulations and overcoming regulatory barriers pose significant challenges for aquaculture operators looking to implement these systems.

In Galician mussel production in Spain, two notable innovations were identified. First, mussel farms are using water quality monitoring systems around mussel rafts to track environmental conditions and optimize mussel growth. This technology allows farmers to ensure the best possible conditions for their operations, improving both yield and sustainability. However, the complexity and cost of the sensor technology, along with the need for technical expertise to operate and maintain the systems, present challenges to broader adoption. The second innovation in Galician mussel farming involves replacing traditional plastic mussel culture pegs with those made from recycled plastic or bio-based materials. This initiative aims to reduce plastic waste in aquaculture by developing environmentally friendly alternatives. The key challenge is finding materials that are durable enough to withstand long-term exposure to marine environments while also being eco-friendly. Ensuring both durability and sustainability in these new materials is crucial for their widespread adoption.

Table 5. Key examples of Innovative ideas in aquatic and water systems

Innovative Idea	Country	Short Description
Seawater Cubes for sustainable aquaculture	Germany	Developing fish farms using Seawater Cubes, creating controlled aquaculture environments.
Fish in aquaculture repurposed as flour/fish oil	Portugal, Greece	Drying and milling rejected fish into flour or fish oil to reduce waste and reuse resources.
Galician mussel production water quality monitoring	Spain	Monitoring water quality around mussel rafts to optimize environmental conditions and mussel growth.
Recycled plastic for mussel culture pegs	Spain	Using recycled plastic or bio-based materials for mussel pegs to reduce plastic waste in aquaculture.

3.2.3.4 Bioenergy

Several innovative bioenergy ideas emerged from the workshops. One prominent idea, explored in Italy and Greece, involves integrated bioenergy systems that use biomass from agricultural and forestry prunings. This concept focuses on supporting local consortia to valorize prunings economically by converting them into bioenergy. However, a significant challenge is the logistical complexity of transporting and processing the biomass.

In Germany and the Netherlands, another key innovation is biogas production from agricultural residues and manure. This approach seeks to integrate circular practices into agriculture by converting residues into biogas, thus reducing agricultural waste while generating renewable energy. The development of CO₂-neutral energy systems using bioenergy and biogas was a prominent idea discussed in Denmark. The concept involves integrating bioenergy and biogas production to create a sustainable, CO₂-neutral energy solution. While the environmental benefits of such systems are clear, the high costs associated with bioenergy and biogas production technologies remain a

significant challenge. For this innovation to gain traction, reducing these costs through technological advancements and financial incentives will be essential.

In Portugal, the use of eucalyptus for energy production was another innovative concept discussed. This approach involves milling eucalyptus bark and branches to extract essential oils, with the remaining biomass being repurposed for bioenergy production. While this dual-purpose method maximizes resource use, the high costs associated with milling eucalyptus make it difficult to scale without financial support or subsidies to assist producers. Overcoming these cost barriers is essential for expanding the adoption of this innovative bioenergy source.

Another notable idea centers around the utilization of ash from biomass burning in power plants. The workshops proposed creating collection centers for ash, which could then be repurposed into soil improvers or other valuable products.

Table 6. Key examples of Innovative ideas in bioenergy systems

Innovative Idea	Country	Short Description
Integrated bioenergy systems using biomass from agricultural and forestry prunings	Italy, Greece	Using biomass from agricultural and forestry prunings to produce bioenergy.
Biogas production from agricultural residues	Germany, Netherlands	Producing biogas by processing agricultural byproducts and manure, reducing waste.
Eucalyptus for energy production	Portugal	Using eucalyptus branches and bark to produce bioenergy and essential oils.
CO2-neutral energy systems with bioenergy	Denmark	Developing CO2-neutral energy production systems through bioenergy and biogas integration.

3.2.3.5 Biomaterials, biobased industries, biorefining

The workshops highlighted several innovative ideas in the realm of bio-based plastics and sustainable materials. One of the key innovations involves the production of PLA (Polylactic Acid) bioplastics in Germany and France. PLA could be derived from renewable feedstocks such as corn starch. However, challenges remain, particularly in defining clear standards for what constitutes "bio-based" and "biodegradable" materials. Additionally, the scalability of PLA production is still limited, with high production costs and technological barriers slowing its widespread adoption.

In Spain, Galician mussel production is exploring a transition from conventional plastic pegs used in aquaculture to recycled or bio-based plastic alternatives. This initiative aims to reduce plastic waste within the aquaculture sector by using more sustainable materials for mussel culture. The primary challenge in this value chain is identifying materials that are not only eco-friendly and biodegradable but also durable enough to withstand prolonged use in harsh marine environments. The durability of bio-based materials remains a significant hurdle for industries dependent on resilient equipment.

Germany also introduced an innovative approach to creating biomaterials through fermentation processes that utilize mine gas as a feedstock. This concept, developed in the Saarland region, focuses on converting non-conventional feedstocks into valuable materials using advanced fermentation techniques. This innovation has the

potential to reduce the environmental footprint of biomaterial production by utilizing otherwise wasted gases. However, refining the fermentation processes and scaling up production to meet industrial demands are significant challenges that need to be addressed before this approach can be adopted more broadly.

Another innovation involves wood-based bioplastics, which have been explored in Denmark and Latvia. By using wood residues as a feedstock, this approach offers a sustainable alternative to conventional plastics, addressing the dual issues of plastic waste and forestry byproducts. The challenge for wood-based bioplastics lies in ensuring that the materials maintain comparable performance to traditional plastics, while also making the production process economically viable for large-scale use.

In Denmark, an innovative value chain centers on creating bio-based adhesives from lignin, a byproduct of wood processing. These bio-based adhesives are designed for use in the wood industry, providing a sustainable alternative to petrochemical-based adhesives. By utilizing lignin, this solution not only addresses waste in the wood industry but also reduces reliance on fossil fuels. The main challenge is in ensuring that bio-based adhesives meet industry performance standards while remaining cost-competitive with traditional adhesives.

Table 7. Key examples of Innovative ideas in biomaterials, biobased industries and biorefining systems

Innovative Idea	Country	Short Description
PLA (Polylactic Acid) Bioplastics	Germany, France	Producing biodegradable bioplastics from renewable feedstocks such as corn starch and sugarcane.
Galician mussel production with recycled plastic pegs	Spain	Replacing conventional plastic mussel culture pegs with recycled or bio-based alternatives.
Biomaterials from fermentation of mine gas	Germany	Creating biomaterials using fermentation processes that utilize mine gas as a feedstock.
Wood-based bioplastics	Denmark, Latvia	Developing bioplastics from wood residues to offer a sustainable alternative to conventional plastics.
Bio-based adhesives from lignin	Denmark	Using lignin, a byproduct of wood, to create sustainable bio-based adhesives for the wood industry.

3.2.4 Ranking of innovative ideas/value chains

Each value chain was ranked based on two indicators (0-10) their impact and feasibility and then assessed for their scalability, value, resource requirements. This process resulted in 10 value chains that scored 9 or above on one of the indicators. For a full ranking please access the following master data excel.

3.3 Challenges identified in the transition to a circular bioeconomy

The workshops revealed a wide range of challenges hindering the transition to circular bioeconomy value chains, with key barriers emerging across several categories. High costs were the most frequently reported challenge, cited 46 times, as stakeholders pointed to the substantial expenses associated with adopting new technologies like

biochar production and bioplastics recycling. Closely following, research gaps were mentioned 37 times, indicating a pressing need for further studies and the development of innovative bio-based products and processes.

Market barriers, such as competition with cheaper, non-circular alternatives, were highlighted 29 times. These challenges underline the difficulty bio-based products face when competing in markets where fossil-based alternatives remain dominant due to lower costs. Regulatory and legal barriers—reported 20 times—were also a significant issue. Stakeholders emphasized problems like unclear waste classification laws and the need for regulatory harmonization across regions and Member States, which often complicates the adoption of circular practices.

Additional challenges included a lack of investment, mentioned 17 times, and processing challenges (14 mentions), such as difficulties in recycling bioplastics. These concerns underscore the critical need for financial support and advancements in residues processing technologies to scale circular solutions. Technological limitations (13 mentions) and price volatility (10 mentions) were also frequently cited, with the lack of biorefinery technologies and fluctuating biomass prices creating significant barriers to the establishment of stable, circular bio-based industries.

Less frequently mentioned but still notable were infrastructure gaps (9 mentions), policy misalignment (7 mentions), and supply chain disruptions (4 mentions). Low consumer awareness of bio-based products and circular systems emerged as a less common challenge, mentioned only once, yet it remains a crucial factor in driving demand and support for circular bioeconomy initiatives.

It is clear that the high costs associated with adopting circular systems represent a long-term issue, but the most revealing discussions from a qualitative analysis centered around regulatory and legal barriers, technological gaps, and logistics challenges. These areas warrant particular attention, as they offer the most potential for impactful intervention and improvement in enabling the circular bioeconomy transition.

Figure 8. Challenges grouped by theme discussed across value chains

3.3.1 Policy and Regulatory Challenges in the transition to a circular bioeconomy

The workshops revealed several policy-related barriers that are impeding the transition to circular bioeconomy value chains. These challenges, primarily linked to unclear waste classifications, inconsistent policies across regions, and the lack of harmonized standards for bio-based products, were frequently mentioned by stakeholders as critical

issues that hinder innovation and scaling of bio-based solutions. Below, we explore each of these points in detail, along with the specific EU policies that contribute to these barriers and the ways forward.

1. Unclear Waste Classifications

One of the most frequently cited challenges was the unclear classification of byproducts or waste streams under existing laws. This ambiguity often leads to difficulties in reusing materials within a circular economy framework. Stakeholders particularly highlighted the EU Waste Framework Directive [6], which establishes rules for waste management but lacks clarity on how certain bio-based residues should be classified. For example, many bio-based residues are still classified as waste, even when they could be repurposed as byproducts or valuable secondary raw materials, complicating their reuse in circular processes.

Furthermore, the End-of-Waste Criteria, which define when waste ceases to be classified as such, are often vague or difficult to apply. This uncertainty creates a bottleneck for companies seeking to incorporate recycled materials into their production processes. Without clear guidance on when a material transitions from waste to product, companies may hesitate to invest in circular practices. Stakeholders suggested that clarifying waste classification rules and streamlining the end-of-waste process would facilitate the reuse of byproducts and reduce regulatory barriers to circular innovation.

2. Inconsistent Policies Across Regions and Sectors

Another significant challenge raised during the workshops was inconsistent regulations across regions and sectors. This lack of uniformity creates confusion for stakeholders, particularly in areas such as waste management, bio-based product certification, and environmental standards. The EU REACH Regulation (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals) was frequently mentioned in this regard [7]. While REACH sets strict requirements for chemicals used in products, it does not adequately differentiate between bio-based and petrochemical-based products. As a result, bio-based innovations often face the same regulatory hurdles as conventional fossil-based products, which can stifle their development and competitiveness.

In addition, participants noted that waste management regulations vary significantly between regions, making it difficult for bio-based companies to scale solutions that rely on consistent handling of materials across borders. This inconsistency particularly affects companies operating in multiple EU countries, where differing rules on bio-based product standards, certification processes, and waste management lead to operational inefficiencies. Stakeholders recommended the creation of consistent, cross-border policies, especially for bio-based product certification and environmental standards, to streamline the adoption of circular practices.

3. Lack of Harmonized Standards for Bio-based Products

The workshops frequently highlighted the lack of harmonized EU standards for bio-based products as a major obstacle to innovation and market scaling. Currently, bio-based products face regulatory uncertainty due to the absence of clear, EU-wide standards that can validate their environmental and performance benefits. This lack of harmonization makes it difficult for bio-based products to compete with conventional alternatives, as producers struggle to meet different regulatory expectations across regions.

For example, stakeholders mentioned that the absence of standardized criteria for bio-based packaging and materials complicates their adoption in industries that require regulatory certainty. Harmonizing these standards across the EU would allow bio-based products to compete more effectively with conventional products and enable more seamless integration into existing value chains. Participants advocated for the development of EU-wide standards for bio-based products to foster innovation, particularly in sectors like packaging and materials.

4. Waste Classification and Management

In addition to the aforementioned EU Waste Framework Directive and End-of-Waste Criteria, stakeholders pointed out that waste classification often remains too rigid to accommodate bio-based innovations. Simplifying waste rules, facilitating classification as by-products or enabling the classification of certain byproducts as secondary raw

materials—rather than waste—could significantly boost recycling and circular practices. Workshops suggested that easing the regulatory burden around waste reuse would encourage companies to adopt more circular strategies, particularly in industries like bioenergy and biomaterials, where byproducts can serve as valuable inputs for new processes.

5. Regulations Around Bio-based Products and Circular Materials

The EU REACH Regulation continues to pose challenges for bio-based innovations by not distinguishing between bio-based and petrochemical-based chemicals. This blanket regulatory approach can unnecessarily hinder the development of bio-based materials, which often have different environmental impacts compared to their fossil-based counterparts. Stakeholders called for more flexibility within REACH to support the unique properties and benefits of bio-based products. Harmonizing standards for bio-based products, including their certification and environmental performance, would help companies innovate and scale circular solutions more effectively.

6. Agricultural and Food Safety Regulations

Agricultural and food safety regulations were also flagged as barriers, particularly for bio-based innovations related to food production. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) [8] promotes sustainability, but some of its rules on land use and resource management restrict the utilization of agricultural byproducts for bio-based products or energy. Workshops noted that EFSA's (European Food Safety Authority) stringent health and safety regulations can make it difficult to incorporate secondary raw materials or waste streams into food-related value chains. Participants called for greater flexibility in agricultural policies to enable the adoption of circular bioeconomy practices, particularly in areas where waste-to-product innovation could reduce environmental impact.

3.3.2 Technological gaps identified

The workshops identified several technological gaps that prevent the transition to a circular bioeconomy across value chains, with processing challenges and infrastructure gaps being the most frequently mentioned areas of concern. Below is an analysis of the key technological gaps highlighted by stakeholders, based on the number of mentions and the specific issues associated with each area.

Processing challenges were the most frequently mentioned technological gap, cited 17 times. Stakeholders reported significant difficulties in recycling and processing materials, particularly within the context of biorefining. These challenges stem from the lack of advanced technologies that can efficiently process bio-based materials or recycle them back into the value chain. Improving biorefining capabilities is critical to enabling more sustainable production systems, yet the complexity of refining bio-based products and the high costs associated with these processes remain major obstacles.

The second most frequently mentioned issue, with 14 mentions, was infrastructure gaps. There is an urgent need for better infrastructure to support the recycling and processing of bio-waste. Participants highlighted the lack of adequate facilities for bio-waste recycling, which hampers the ability to valorize organic waste and transform it into valuable products. Developing specialized infrastructure for bio-based industries is essential to facilitate circular systems, but high capital costs and logistical challenges are slowing down the expansion of such infrastructure.

Waste valorization technologies, cited 4 times, were another notable gap. Stakeholders expressed concerns about the insufficient technologies available for recycling or valorizing organic residues. Valorization processes, which could convert residues into energy, bio-based products, or materials, are still in the early stages of development for many sectors. Without these technologies, large amounts of bio-residues remain unused, representing a missed opportunity for circular resource use. Further investment and research in waste valorization technologies are needed to unlock their potential.

Aquaculture technologies were mentioned 3 times, with stakeholders identifying gaps in the processing of fish residues into bio-based products. The aquaculture sector has the potential to contribute to the circular bioeconomy by transforming fish waste into valuable materials, such as fertilizers or bio-based chemicals. However, the lack of technologies to efficiently process this residue limits the sector's ability to fully participate in circular systems.

Addressing these gaps through technological innovation will help reduce waste and improve resource efficiency in aquaculture.

Water-saving technologies were cited 2 times as a critical need for improving resource efficiency in agriculture. Technologies that enhance water use efficiency are essential for sustainable farming practices, particularly in regions facing water scarcity. The workshops noted that current technologies for conserving water are insufficient and need further development to support more sustainable agricultural production systems.

Finally, energy efficiency innovations were mentioned once, highlighting the need for new technologies that improve energy use in bio-based industries. Energy consumption is a significant factor in the sustainability of bio-based production systems, and stakeholders expressed a need for technologies that can reduce energy inputs while maintaining production efficiency. Innovations in this area are crucial to lowering the environmental footprint of bio-based industries.

Figure 9. Technological gaps mentioned and sorted by theme

4. Discussion and conclusions

The following section discusses the main results and their implications for the transition to a circular bioeconomy, as derived from the 43 workshops. It covers key barriers identified by stakeholders, such as high costs, technological limitations, and logistical challenges, particularly in the management of waste and feedstocks, policy insights, the importance of research and innovation in overcoming technological gaps, and the role of local bioeconomy clusters.

4.1 Key barriers to the development of circular value chains

It is not surprising that high costs emerged as the main barrier to the transition to a circular bioeconomy, given the capital-intensive nature of developing and scaling bio-based solutions. Circular bioeconomy systems, by their very design, require substantial upfront investments in technology, infrastructure, and research and development. Whether it's the construction of biorefineries, the adoption of advanced recycling technologies, or the establishment of bio-waste processing facilities, the costs associated with these transitions are far higher than those involved in maintaining traditional, linear value chains. These systems often rely on inexpensive fossil-based materials and established processes that have been in place for decades. In contrast, circular bioeconomy practices involve longer-term investments, with returns that may only materialize over extended periods.

Moreover, the cost of feedstock for bio-based industries tends to be higher than that of fossil-based alternatives, particularly when accounting for the logistics and processing required to turn biomass into usable products. Bio-based products are often more expensive to produce because of the complex supply chains required to source, transport, and refine bio-based materials. Additionally, bio-based industries frequently lack the economies of scale enjoyed by fossil-based industries, which have long benefited from infrastructure and global supply chains optimized for their needs. In a market environment where cost competitiveness is critical, it is understandable that stakeholders would identify costs as a fundamental barrier to adopting circular practices.

The workshops also highlighted the fact that high costs are not just tied to technology and infrastructure but also to compliance with regulatory frameworks. Circular bioeconomy systems often require adherence to more stringent environmental regulations, as well as investments in certification and compliance for bio-based products. These added layers of regulation and certification further raise the cost of operating within a circular system, making it challenging for many businesses to justify the initial investments without stronger market incentives or government support. All of these factors combined make it clear why high costs are perceived as the most significant barrier to the widespread adoption of a circular bioeconomy.

Another main identified challenge, feedstock logistics, was clearly identified across workshops. Feedstock logistics are particularly challenging for bio-based value chains due to the decentralized and variable nature of biomass sources. Unlike fossil-based raw materials, which can be extracted from concentrated reserves and transported efficiently through established infrastructure, bio-based feedstocks are often distributed across large, rural areas and vary seasonally. This creates difficulties in collecting, transporting, and processing the biomass. Additionally, the bulkiness and perishability of many bio-based materials, such as agricultural residues or organic waste, further complicate logistics, as they require specialized handling, storage, and timely transportation. Furthermore, ensuring a reliable, year-round supply of diverse feedstocks to biorefineries adds an additional layer of complexity, making logistics a significant barrier to the efficient functioning of bio-based value chains [9].

Technological gaps and limitations were also identified as significant barriers to the development and scaling of bio-based value chains. Many of the processes required to convert biomass into valuable products, such as biorefining, biofuel production, or bioplastic manufacturing, are still in their early stages and often lack cost-effectiveness compared to established fossil-based processes. For example, the technologies needed to efficiently extract, process, and refine diverse types of biomass are not yet fully mature, leading to high operational costs and limited output. Furthermore, waste valorization technologies—needed to convert agricultural or industrial waste into valuable bio-based products—are still underdeveloped, which limits the ability to turn byproducts into new resources [10].

4.2 Waste prevention and use of existing residues

A significant focus across the workshops was on residue management, with numerous ideas centered around the reuse or repurposing of residue from existing value chains for other processes or products. This strong emphasis on residue management highlights the critical importance stakeholders place on making the most of existing resources, particularly as the shift towards a circular bioeconomy continues. Interestingly, this focus on residue reuse surpassed other potential themes, such as the development of sustainable feedstocks, which one might expect to be a more prominent area of concern in bio-based systems. This prioritization of residue management suggests that achieving a fully circular economy will require addressing inefficiencies in current systems. The reuse of waste in bio-based value chains is seen as a crucial step toward reducing reliance on virgin materials and minimizing the environmental impact of industries, particularly those with heavy resource demands. It also signals a shift in focus from just producing bio-based alternatives to integrating waste valorization technologies and processes that can extend the lifecycle of materials.

It is clear from the workshops that bioeconomy feedstocks are limited in availability, and that the potential reuse of residues into a range of other products can significantly improve overall economic efficiency. The emphasis on residues reuse underscores the idea that we may not need as many virgin feedstocks as we often assume. By focusing on valorizing residues streams, industries can extract more value from the same resources, effectively extending the lifecycle of feedstocks and reducing the need for fresh raw materials. This approach not only promotes sustainability but also reduces the environmental impact of extracting and processing new materials, offering a more circular and efficient bioeconomy.

The approach is also completely aligned with the waste management hierarchy defined by the EU Waste Framework Directive [6] which clearly states that preventing waste is the preferred option.

4.3 Policy Insights in the transition to a circular bioeconomy

The workshops highlighted several key policy-related barriers that are hindering the development of circular bioeconomy value chains. Stakeholders frequently raised concerns about unclear waste classifications, inconsistent policies across regions, and the lack of harmonized standards for bio-based products. These issues create significant regulatory obstacles for bio-based innovation and limit the scaling of sustainable solutions.

One major challenge is the unclear classification of byproducts and waste. The EU Waste Framework Directive, byproducts and End-of-Waste Criteria [6] were frequently cited for their ambiguity, leading to confusion about when a residue can be classified as a byproduct or when materials can transition from being classified as waste to usable products. This regulatory uncertainty discourages investment in circular practices. Clarifying these rules would make it easier for companies to reuse byproducts, thus reducing waste and encouraging circularity.

Additionally, inconsistent policies across EU regions make it difficult for bio-based industries to scale. Differences in waste management regulations, bio-based product certification, and environmental standards lead to inefficiencies for companies operating across multiple countries. For example, the EU REACH Regulation does not differentiate adequately between bio-based and fossil-based chemicals, applying the same stringent rules to both [7]. This lack of flexibility hampers the development of bio-based innovations, making it harder for companies to compete with fossil-based products. Stakeholders recommended the creation of consistent, cross-border policies, particularly for certification and environmental standards, to streamline the adoption of circular practices.

Another significant barrier is the lack of harmonized standards for bio-based products across the EU. The absence of EU-wide criteria for bio-based packaging and materials creates uncertainty, making it challenging for companies to compete with conventional alternatives. Harmonizing these standards would provide clarity and support the growth of bio-based industries.

Agricultural and food safety regulations also present obstacles, especially for innovations related to food production. While the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) promotes sustainability, certain rules limit the use of

agricultural byproducts in bio-based products or energy [8]. Similarly, EFSA’s stringent safety standards make it difficult to incorporate secondary raw materials into food-related value chains. Stakeholders called for greater regulatory flexibility to enable circular bioeconomy practices in agriculture, particularly in areas where waste-to-product innovation can reduce environmental impacts.

Key Takeaways and Ways Forward

- **Harmonization of Standards:** There is a pressing need for harmonized EU standards for bio-based products to encourage innovation and scaling. This would provide regulatory clarity, reduce market barriers, and allow bio-based products to compete with conventional alternatives.
- **Simplification of Waste Rules:** Stakeholders urged for simplified waste classification rules and clearer end-of-waste criteria to enable the reuse of byproducts and improve recycling rates. This would remove unnecessary regulatory hurdles and facilitate the transition to circular value chains.
- **Innovation-friendly Policies:** To support the EU’s bioeconomy goals, policies need to be more innovation-friendly, particularly in the areas of bio-based materials and circular product design. Adjustments to REACH and the introduction of harmonized certification standards for bio-based products are critical to fostering a more supportive regulatory environment.

Based on the outputs from the workshops it appears that addressing these policy-related challenges as shown in Table 7 will help accelerate the transition to a circular bioeconomy across biobased value chains.

Table 8. Regulatory Challenges identified, their relation to EU policy and takeaways

Regulatory Challenge Identified	Related EU Policy	Suggested Takeaway / Way to Move Forward
Unclear Waste Classifications	EU Waste Framework Directive, End-of-Waste Criteria	Clarify waste classification, byproducts and end-of-waste criteria to facilitate reuse of residues.
Inconsistent Policies	EU REACH Regulation, Waste Framework Directive	Create consistent policies across regions and sectors, particularly for certification and standards.
Lack of Harmonization	Standards for Bio-based Products, EU Harmonization Directives	Harmonize EU standards for bio-based products to encourage innovation and scale.
Waste Classification and Management	EU Waste Framework Directive, End-of-Waste Criteria	Simplify waste rules and classifications to enable better recycling and circular use of materials.
Regulations Around Bio-based Products and Circular Materials	EU REACH Regulation, Standards for Bio-based Products	Support bio-based innovations by adjusting REACH and setting harmonized standards for bio-based products.
Agricultural and Food Safety Regulations	Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), Food Safety Standards (EFSA)	Relax some restrictions to allow bio-based innovations, particularly in food and agriculture.

4.4 The Importance of Research and Innovation in Overcoming Technological Gaps

Research and innovation play a critical role in overcoming the technological gaps that currently impede the transition to a circular bioeconomy. As highlighted in the workshops, many of the barriers to implementing circular value chains are directly linked to insufficient or underdeveloped technologies, particularly in areas such as biorefineries, residue valorization, and processing of bio-based materials. Investing in research and development

in biobased value chains (R&D) is essential not only to create more efficient technologies but also to reduce the long-term costs of transitioning to sustainable systems.

One of the key areas where research is needed is in the development of advanced biorefineries that can process multiple types of biomass into a diverse range of products. Integrated biorefineries that are capable of efficiently converting agricultural, forestry, and other organic residues into valuable products like biofuels, bioplastics, and chemicals are critical for reducing waste and increasing resource efficiency. However, current technologies are often too costly or limited in scope to fully realize the potential of these systems. By directing research towards improving the scalability and efficiency of biorefining technologies, the industry can achieve economies of scale, which in turn will help to drive down the cost of bio-based products, making them more competitive with fossil-based alternatives. The EU is currently doing this through various funding programs and initiatives, such as Horizon Europe and the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU), which aim to support research and innovation in biorefining technologies. These programs are designed to foster collaboration between research institutions, industry, and policymakers to accelerate the development of advanced biorefineries that can process a diverse range of biomass more efficiently and cost-effectively [11].

Additionally, innovation in residues valorization technologies is crucial for creating new opportunities in circular value chains. Stakeholders repeatedly pointed to the lack of effective technologies for recycling or repurposing organic residues, indicating that there is untapped potential in converting residue streams into valuable feedstocks. Research should focus on developing cost-effective residues processing technologies, as well as methods for valorizing more complex organic residues.

The workshops also identified processing challenges, such as the difficulty of refining bio-based materials or recycling bioplastics, as a significant technological gap. Here again, research into more efficient and sustainable processing technologies will be key to lowering production costs in the long term. For example, by developing biodegradable plastics that are easier and cheaper to recycle, the industry could dramatically reduce its reliance on expensive processing methods.

Moreover, technological innovation has the potential to reduce the costs associated with logistics and infrastructure. Many bio-based industries currently face high costs due to the need for specialized facilities and transportation systems for bio-based products and residues. Research into more efficient logistics models and the development of modular processing technologies that can be implemented in decentralized locations could help lower these costs and make circular systems more accessible to rural and remote areas. This, in turn, would foster the development of regional bioindustry clusters, where multiple bio-based businesses can share resources and infrastructure.

4.5 The importance of local bioeconomy hubs and clusters

An interesting outcome of the workshops is the combined strong emphasis on residues reuse, alongside the identification of high costs and challenges related to logistics and feedstock processing. This focus suggests that stakeholders recognize the importance of achieving a local critical mass for circular value chains to function effectively. Rather than viewing bio-based industries in isolation, there is a clear understanding that for circular systems to thrive, there must be a convergence of sufficient feedstock availability, efficient logistics, and a concentration of bio-based industries working in close proximity.

For instance, stakeholders highlighted the potential of integrated biorefineries or integrated bioindustries, where various types of biomass—ranging from agricultural residues to forestry byproducts—can be processed into a wide array of bio-based products, including biofuels, chemicals, and bioplastics. These integrated systems are more efficient because they maximize the use of available feedstocks and produce multiple outputs, thereby increasing the economic viability of bio-based industries.

The concept of bioeconomy clusters—where multiple industries within the bioeconomy work synergistically—seems to be a key recommendation. Such clusters would allow for shared infrastructure, optimized logistics, and more efficient processing, ultimately lowering costs and fostering innovation. By concentrating bio-based activities

in specific regions, these clusters could help overcome the high costs and logistical difficulties that currently hinder the scalability of circular value chains. This insight emphasizes that for a circular bioeconomy to succeed, stakeholders must focus on regional collaboration and infrastructure development, ensuring that industries can operate as part of an interconnected system rather than in isolation [12].

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this deliverable documents and analyzes the results from BioRural's 43 national workshops, providing insights into the challenges and opportunities in transitioning to a circular bioeconomy. The workshops explored over 140 individual value chains, generating a wide range of innovative ideas as well as identifying key barriers that need to be addressed for the bioeconomy to thrive.

The main innovations emerging from the workshops were centered around 'waste' management and the reuse of residues and byproducts from existing value chains. This focus reflects the importance of maximizing resource efficiency by repurposing byproducts and waste to create new bio-based products. Innovations in this area aimed to reduce waste while creating valuable products, such as bioenergy and bioplastics, from byproducts of agricultural, forestry, and industrial activities. Another prominent theme was the development of sustainable materials, with many ideas focused on replacing conventional fossil-based materials with bio-based alternatives. The main bio-based product ideas revolved around agricultural products, such as bio-based fertilizers, bioplastics made from agricultural residues, and bioenergy from crop residues, which were seen as essential for reducing the environmental impact of current production systems.

The main challenges identified during the workshops included high costs associated with transitioning to and implementing circular value chains, significant research and technological gaps, and regulatory barriers that impede the development and scaling of bio-based innovations. High costs were particularly tied to the logistics of feedstock collection, the development of processing technologies, and the lack of infrastructure necessary to support circular systems. Research gaps were also highlighted, particularly in areas such as biorefining technologies and residues valorization processes, where current technologies are not yet efficient or scalable enough to meet industry needs. Additionally, regulatory challenges—such as unclear waste classifications, byproducts definitions and inconsistent policies across regions—further complicated the adoption of circular bio-based practices.

To overcome these barriers, several key solutions were proposed. First, there is a need to simplify and clarify regulations, particularly around waste management and the classification of bio-based products, to encourage the reuse of byproducts and streamline circular practices. Stakeholders also suggested continued support for research and innovation, especially in closing technological gaps related to processing efficiencies, advanced biorefineries, and recycling technologies. Investment in these areas will be critical to reducing the costs of bio-based products and making circular systems more competitive with conventional alternatives. In addition, fostering regional bioeconomy clusters, where local industries can collaborate to share resources and infrastructure, was seen as an effective strategy for addressing logistical challenges and promoting the growth of circular value chains.

Overall, the insights gained from these workshops provide a foundation for shaping future policy recommendations coming out of the BioRural Project and accelerate the transition to a more circular bioeconomy.

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7. Annex I: Workshop Reports and additional materials

7.1 National multi-actor innovation workshop reports

The full English version of the canvas can be accessed following this link: [\[ORIGINAL ENG\] BioRural National Workshops Canvas.pdf](#)

The 43 individual workshop reports can be accessed following this link: [National Workshop Reports](#)

The master excel document combining all key workshop results can be accessed following this link: [National Workshop results master document](#)

7.2 What are biobased solutions

Bio-based solutions are innovative technologies, processes and/or end-products based on circularity that produce or utilise biomass sustainably as compared to mainstream technologies or processes that produce non-innovative end products or utilise biomass without significant innovations or sustainable outputs. An adopter must either produce an innovative/sustainable biobased end-product or use a sustainable technology or sustainable process during the production of a biobased product.

In particular, for the **production** of raw biomass/feedstocks we consider sustainable practices and technologies to be biobased solutions. For the **processing** of biomass/feedstocks we consider sustainable technologies, processes and end products to be biobased solutions. This distinction exists as in the production of biobased feedstocks it is generally the process and technologies used in the producing of the feedstock that determines its level of sustainability/circularity. While for processed and finished products it's a combination of efficient production systems (efficient technologies and processes) and the production of a sustainable bio end-product that distinguishes it from mainstream/traditional processing practices.

A detailed description of biobased solutions with key thematic examples can be accessed following this link: